

determined cryoscopically using Beckmann thermometer of accuracy 0.01° . The infrared spectra in nujol were recorded in the range $4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ using Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer.

Materials: The Lewis acids employed in this investigation were prepared according to the reported methods⁴. Diethyl amine (BDH) was used.

Preparation of the complexes: Excess of a solution of the amine in diethyl ether was added to about 2 m mole of diaryl tin dihalide in the same solvent. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed several times with the same solvent and dried in vacuum. The experimental results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR $R_2SnX_2 \cdot 2Et_2NH$

R	X	m.p. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	analysis %		Found (Calc.)	
			Sn	C	H	N
phenyl	Cl	162	24.10 (24.28)	48.52 (48.93)	6.25 (6.53)	5.51 (5.72)
			o-tolyl	Cl	196	22.62 (22.97)
Br	224	19.19 (19.60)				43.12 (43.49)
		I	184	16.51 (17.00)	37.27 (37.72)	5.19 (5.14)
m-tolyl	Cl			176	22.55 (22.97)	50.56 (50.96)
		p-tolyl	Cl		180	22.43 (22.97)
Br	194			19.21 (19.60)		43.32 (43.49)
		I	191	17.12 (17.00)	37.26 (37.72)	5.22 (5.14)

The complexes possess 1 : 2 stoichiometry. They are white crystalline solids, thermally stable with sharp melting points and are soluble in nitrobenzene.

The molar conductances of 10^{-3} M solution of the complexes in nitrobenzene, observed below $5\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mole}^{-1}$, indicate absence of ionic species. However experimentally determined molecular weight of some of the complexes is considerably lower than the formula weight indicating significant decomposition of the complexes in solution.

Infrared spectra: A comparison of the spectra of the complexes with that of the free base indicates distinct lowering of the N-H stretching frequency from 3335 cm^{-1} to $3190 \pm 30\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The asymmetric and symmetric $\nu\text{C-N}$ identified at 1148 and 890 cm^{-1} respectively in the spectrum of diethyl amine also undergo negative shift to the extent of 108 ± 5 and $65 \pm 35\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The changes indicate the presence of co-ordinated base. In the far IR region, the identification of two new absorptions at 427 ± 13 and $364 \pm 12\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectrum of the complexes are attributed to $\nu(\text{Sn-N})$ stretching vibration, which is a direct evidence for coordination

from the nitrogen atom of the base^{6,7}. Three other distinct absorptions occurring at 286 ± 9 , 257 ± 8 and 248 ± 6 are assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn-C})$, $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{Sn-Cl})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{Sn-Cl})$ respectively.⁸⁻⁹ $\nu(\text{Sn-Br})$ and $\nu(\text{Sn-I})$ are expected to lie beyond the recorded range of the spectra.

The analytical, infrared, and conductivity data indicate hexa co-ordinated octahedral compounds.

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Alkali Metal Complexes : Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of some Organic Acids with Bidentate Chelating Diol

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SIDGWICK and Brewer¹ first reported that hydrated salts of sodium benzoylacetone was soluble in toluene and benzene, had a sharp melting point and lost water above 115° . Similar observations were also recorded by them about the dihydrates of lithium methyl salicylate (Li. MS), lithium salicylaldehyde and sodium acetylacetonate. Nyholm and others² also recorded that anhydrous red potassium-*o*-nitrophenolate (K. ONP) changed to orange monohydrate on exposure to atmosphere. That the above mentioned compounds were coordinated complexes was based on a) solubility

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in non-polar solvents and b) the compounds have sharp melting points and lost water well over 100°. This argument was considered to be unsatisfactory because of the possibility that water was not coordinated, but present as water of crystallisation. In order to eliminate water from the system, it would be convenient to use a bidentate chelating diol, such as 1,2-ethanediol (ethyleneglycol).

Experimental

(I) *Li. Sal. glycol*: The pale yellow crystals of Li. salicylaldehyde dihydrate were dehydrated by heating in an air oven at 125° for 1 hr. These deep yellow crystals were then suspended in acetone and ethyleneglycol was added dropwise with stirring, when salt in suspension was solubilised (addition of ethyleneglycol in excess was avoided). Then on stirring for a couple of minutes more, a white compound separated out. It was then filtered, washed carefully with acetone and then dried in oven at 80°.

[Found: C, 55.9; H, 6.1 per cent. Calc. for $C_9H_{11}O_4Li$: C, 56.8; H, 5.8 percent].

(II) *Li. MS. glycol*: The method of preparation was exactly similar to the above, except that the compound (white) could be isolated from a mixture of chloroform and absolute ethanol (4:1) as it was very soluble in acetone or ethanol.

[Found: C, 55.2; H, 5.5 per cent; Calc. for $C_{10}H_{13}O_5Li$: C, 54.5; H, 5.9 per cent]

(III) *K. ONP. glycol*: The anhydrous red K. *o*-nitrophenolate was suspended in a mixture of chloroform and absolute ethanol (4:1) and ethyleneglycol was added to it dropwise. The colour of the salt immediately changed to orange yellow. The mixture was refluxed with stirring for 20 min for complete transformation and then filtered, washed and dried as mentioned above. [Found: C, 39.6; H, 4.5; N, 6.1; K, 16.7 per cent. Calc. for $C_8H_{10}NO_5K$: C, 40.1; H, 4.2; N, 5.9; K, 16.3 per cent.].

Results and Discussion

We have prepared the complexes of ethyleneglycol with lithium methylsalicylate, lithium salicylaldehyde

and potassium-*o*-nitrophenolate, starting material being their anhydrous salts. Although it is possible to replace coordinated water directly by glycol in "heavy" metal complexes³, the anhydrous salts, obtained after heating the hydrated salts at 125° for 1 hr. were used in order to give the glycol a better chance of coordination with alkali metals.

The glycol complexes are rapidly hydrolysed by exposure to moisture but are stable in dry, oxygen-free atmosphere.

If LiSal. $2H_2O$ is heated slowly, it changes colour from pale yellow to deep yellow at about 120° due to the production of the anhydrous salt, followed by charring at 190°-92°. Li. Sal. glycol, white in colour, decomposes at 154°-56°. Anhydrous L. methylsalicylate (white) decomposes at 204°-6°, whereas the corresponding glycol complex melts with decomposition at 162°-63°. The K. ONP melts at 235° and its glycol complex has a transition temperature at 200° when the colour changes from orange-yellow to red, and finally the red salt (K. ONP) melts at 235°, suggesting that the glycol molecule is attached to K. ONP, which can be easily cleaved.

Infra-red Spectra: The infra-red spectra in Nujol mulls of the anhydrous metal salts, the dihydrates, the glycol complexes and glycol complexes $[Co(glycol)_3]Br_3$ and sodiumbenzoylacetoneglycol, in which glycol is known to be coordinated⁴, were recorded in the region 4000-650 cm^{-1} .

The spectra of the complexes, in general, proved to be similar to the spectra of the organic acid metal salts with the addition of bands due to the ligand molecules. The spectra of the metal acid salts differ from that of the acid. The presence of the coordinated glycol is inferred by comparing the glycol peaks in the complexes, $[Co(glycol)_3]Br_3$, Na(bzac) glycol, and glycol itself (Table 1). Bands due to O-H bending vibrations are obscured by ligand vibrations. However, the following frequencies recorded in Table 1 can be identified. In the spectra of Li. MS. glycol, the broad absorption between 3300-3100 cm^{-1} with two humps at 2740 cm^{-1} and 2640 cm^{-1} suggest that apart from coordination of the O-H groups, there is also hydrogen bonding between different groups.

TABLE 1—GLYCOL VIBRATIONS IN CM^{-1}

	(O-H) str	(C-O) str	(CH ₂) rock
Glycol	3330	1086 1040	882 863
Co(glycol) ₃ Br ₃	3280	1077, 1065 1035	877 858
Na(bzac)glycol	3305, 3260	1088 1035	884 859
Ca(bzac)glycol	3300	1099 1036	889 860
Li.MS.glycol	3150br 2740 2640	1075 1045 1032	870 863
Li.Sal.glycol	3290	1075 1045	892 865
K.ONP.glycol	3170	1048 1040	890 860

A crystal structure analysis⁵ of a compound of ethyleneglycol with sodiumbenzoylacetate has shown that the glycol molecule, while coordinated, is not chelated but bridging two sodium atoms. Similar structure is suggested for these alkali metal complexes in view of the similarity of the compounds.

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Complex Formation of Lanthanum with β -Resorcylic Acid

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β -RESORCYLIC acid (H_3RSA) figures prominently in the discussion of hydroxy carboxylic acids and provides two possible co-ordination sites, viz, -COOH and -OH groups, which have attracted the attention of many workers to explore the interaction of this acid with many metal ions¹⁻⁶. A close examination of the existing literature reveals the absence of any study on this system. Hence the present investigations have been carried out.

Experimental

AnalaR (B. D. H.) reagents sodium hydroxide, lanthanum nitrate and Fluka's β -resorcylic acid, were used. A cambridge pH meter was used to determine the H^+ concentration of the reaction mixtures.

Conductance measurements were carried out by a conductometer (WTW Leitfähigkeitsmesser, type LBR, made in Germany) with magic eye as a visual indicator.

The experimental procedure consisted of potentiometric and conductometric titrations of ligand in the absence and presence of Lanthanum nitrate against standard alkali.

Results and Discussion

The appearance of inflections and breaks after the addition of one and two moles of alkali per mole of ligand (Fig. 1, curves 1 and 1') correspond respectively to the neutralisation of carboxyl and *p*-phenolic groups.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric and conductometric titration curves of H_3RSA in the absence & presence of $La(III)$ with $0.1M$ $NaOH$. Curves 1 & 1' : $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ H_3RSA ; curves 2 & 2' : $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ $H_3RSA + 5 \times 10^{-3}M$ $La(III)$; curves 3 & 3' : $1 \times 10^{-2}M$ $H_3RSA + 5 \times 10^{-3}M$ $La(III)$.

When 1 : 1 mixture of ligand and metal is titrated against standard alkali (curve-2) no complex formation was observed till pH 7.0, but above this pH, the affinity of ligand for metal increases, as a result of which a decrease in the corresponding pH values is observed. An inflection at m=4 corresponds to the formation of 1 : 1 hydroxo complex and neutralisation of *p*-OH group of the ligand. The reaction may be represented as :

2 : 1 mixture of ligand and metal (curve-3) against standard alkali indicates two inflections at m=2 and m=6. The first corresponds to the neutralisation of -COOH groups and the second inflection corresponds to the formation of 1 : 1 hydroxo-complex and neutralisation of *p*-OH groups of the ligand.

The precipitation begins to appear above pH 7.0

The composition was further confirmed by conductometric titrations. The breaks at m=1 and m=4 in the 1 : 1 mixture of ligand and metal against standard alkali (curve 2'), clearly indicates the neutralisation of -COOH